

Infra-red Bandshift due to Chelation in Coumarin Bonds

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The I.R. absorption band of a ketonic carbonyl function in coumarin nucleus shifts to a lower frequency due to the presence of a hydroxyl group or a methoxyl group at its *o*-position. The extent of band shift depends on (i) the bond order of the bond on which the two groups are present, and (ii) steric effect due to the presence of a third group on either side of the interacting groups.

The magnitude of shift to lower frequency ($\Delta\nu_{\text{C=O}}$) exhibited by the $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ absorption band (in the infra-red) in going from I to the corresponding II is a measure of the strength of an intramolecular hydrogen bond in an aromatic system such as II¹.

A shift of IR band of $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ group to lower frequency has however been attributed to factors other than hydrogen bonding e.g., resonance interaction² between $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ and a group situated at the ortho position of the carbonyl bearing carbon.

The strength of hydrogen bond has been postulated to depend primarily on two factors (1) bond order of the ring bond between carbon atoms bearing the chelating substituents¹ and (2) steric interaction with groups situated at ortho position of the chelating groups¹.

The present paper deals with the measurement of IR absorption-band shift of chelated $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ bonds, the substituents being on bonds A, B, C, and D respectively of coumarin III.

DISCUSSION

The bond orders of the bonds, A, B, C, D as calculated by S. Isaac³ have been presented in III along with the electron densities on different atoms in the ground state.

1. I. M. Hunsberger, H. S. Gutowsky, W. Powell, L. Morin and V. Bandurco, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 3294.
2. D. Heinert and A. E. Martell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 3933.
3. S. Isaac, *Compt. rend.*, 1955, **240**, 2534.

Correlation of bond order and other factors, with magnitude of band shift has also been attempted.

Fig. III

Synthetic Works : 6-Acetyl-5-hydroxy-4-methyl⁴, 6-acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl⁵, 8-acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl⁶, 8-acetyl-7-hydroxy-coumarin⁷ and 3-acetyl-4-hydroxy-coumarin⁸ were prepared according to methods described in the literature. Their methyl ethers were prepared by treatment with dimethyl sulphate and potassium carbonate in anhydrous acetone.

6-Acetyl-5-hydroxy; 6-acetyl-5-methoxy; 6-acetyl-7-hydroxy; 8-acetyl-6-ethyl-5-hydroxy; 6-acetyl-5-hydroxy-3,4-dihydro, 6-acetyl-7-hydroxy-3,4-dihydrocoumarin have been prepared in our laboratory^{9,10}.

8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-3,4-dihydrocoumarin has been synthesised by condensing 2,6-dihydroxy-acetophenone and acrylonitrile with AlCl_3 . The product on dehydrogenation with Pd/C in diphenyl oxide gave 8-acetyl-7-hydroxycoumarin, which was identical with a product obtained by Fries rearrangement of 7-acetoxycoumarin⁷. The methylether of 3-acetyl-4-hydroxycoumarin has not been reported in the literature. 4-Hydroxy-3-acetylcoumarin, however, resisted all attempts of methylation by conventional methods viz., CH_3I , NaOEt; sodium dust in benzene and methyl iodide; dimethyl sulphate and K_2CO_3 in acetone, methylethyl ketone etc. The resistance to methylation may be due to the reason that the hydrogen bonding is very strong. 3-Acetylcoumarin was prepared by condensing salicylaldehyde and ethyl acetoacetate.

Infra-red work : The infra-red absorption spectra of all the methoxy- and hydroxy-acetyl coumarins have α -pyrone $> \text{C}=\text{O}$ band at $1720\text{--}1730\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is frequently split¹¹. The 3,4-dihydrocoumarins have lactonic carbonyl band at 1775 cm^{-1} .

4. A. Schiavello and C. Sebastiani, *Gazz. Chim. ital.*, 1951, **81**, 492.
5. R. D. Desai and S. A. Hamid, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1937, **6A**, 185.
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10. D. Chatterjee and K. Sen, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 424.
11. K. Nakanishi, *Infra-red Absorption Spectroscopy*, Nankoda Company Limited, Tokyo, 1962, 52.

The carbonyl bands of all the acetylcoumarins as well as those of acetophenone, *o*-hydroxy- and *o*-methoxy acetophenone are presented in Table 1. The $\Delta\nu_{c=0}$ values are also presented in the same table.

TABLE 1

Carbonyl frequencies and $\Delta\nu_{c=0}$ values for acetylated coumarin derivatives in chloroform.

Sl. No.	Compounds ^a Coumarin III	> C = 0 cm ⁻¹		Bond ^a	$\Delta\nu_{c=0}$
		Lactone	Ketone		
1.	6-Acetyl-5-hydroxy-4-methyl	1720	1630	A	50
2.	6-Acetyl-5-methoxy-4-methyl	1720	1680		
3.	6-Acetyl-5-hydroxy	1727	1630	A	37 13 ^c
4.	6-Acetyl-5-methoxy	1742 ^b 1724	1667		
5.	6-Acetyl-5-hydroxy-3,4-dihydro	1775	1630		
6.	6-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl	1735 ^b 1715	1635	B	35
7.	6-Acetyl-7-methoxy-4-methyl	1720	1670		
8.	6-Acetyl-7-hydroxy	1735	1635	B	35
9.	6-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-3,4-dihydro	1780	1635		
10.	8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl	1725	1620	C	70
11.	8-Acetyl-7-methoxy-4-methyl	1725 ^b 1710	1690		
12.	8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy	1735	1620	C	70
13.	8-Acetyl-7-methoxy	1730 ^b 1705	1690		
14.	8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-3,4-dihydro	1775	1620		
15.	8-Acetyl-5-hydroxy-6-ethyl	1724	1690		
16.	3-Acetyl-4-hydroxy	1720	1615	D	71
17.	3-Acetyl	1721	1686		
18.	Acetophenone		1680		45
19.	2-Hydroxyacetophenone		1635	Aromatic	30 15 ^d
20.	2-Methoxyacetophenone		1665		

(^a) The numbering are with reference to structure III.

(^b) Split band.

(^c) Between compound 2 and 4.

(^d) Between compounds 18 and 20.

The infra-red spectra of *o*-hydroxy-acetyl-3,4-dihydrocoumarins have been included to substantiate the fact that the band at lower frequency is due to the chelated carbonyl function and not due to C = C which should also show a band in that region. In fact the C = C band of most of the coumarins appear at 1600 cm⁻¹, ~ 1604 cm⁻¹ just below the chelated carbonyl bands which disappear in case of the corresponding dihydro-compounds.

The calculated bond orders for the different bonds in coumarin are in the order D > A > C > B. The last three have values very close to that of normal benzene bond. The bond order of bond D shows that its double bond character is much higher. But from the data given in Table 1 it emerges, however, that the $\Delta\nu_{c=0}$ values for different bonds are in the order.

$$D > C > A > B$$

Moreover, the $\Delta\nu_{c=0}$ values for bond C and bond A are much higher than that of a normal aromatic bond. The only bond which has comparable value with a benzenoid bond is bond B whose bond order is also nearest to that of benzene.

The anomalous results point that, factors other than bond order also contribute to the magnitude of $\Delta\nu_{c=0}$.

In case of bond C a strongly negative oxygen atom (position 1) causes repulsion of the acetyl > C = O group (at position 8) which is pushed towards -OH group resulting in a stronger hydrogen bonding and hence a larger band shift of > C = O towards lower frequency (1620 cm⁻¹) by 15 cm⁻¹ than the usual shift due to chelation on a benzene bond (1635 cm⁻¹).

Introduction of a methoxy group at the ortho position of a > C = O group causes a shift towards lower frequency (acetophenone, 1680 cm⁻¹; *o*-methoxyacetophenone, 1665 cm⁻¹) by 15 cm⁻¹. In case of coumarins this value should be of the order of 25 cm⁻¹ since a carbonyl group, placed on the aromatic nucleus of coumarin ring, which is not hydrogen-bonded has band at 1690-1707 cm⁻¹ viz., IR band of 8-acetyl-5-hydroxy-6-ethyl-4-methyl-coumarin¹⁰ and those of acylated coumarins described by Woods and Williams¹². This phenomenon has been attributed by Heinert and Martell² to resonance interaction between > C = O and methoxyl group. It has also been shown² that the magnitude of $\Delta\nu_{c=0}$ due to resonance interaction is diminished if there is a repulsion of > C = O by a group situated at the *o*-position of the C-atom to which it is attached. This diminution is said to be due to the fact² that a > C = O group on being repulsed assumes a less coplanar conformation allowing less resonance interaction. This effect is manifested by a band shift of > C = O to higher frequency than the frequency of aromatic ortho-methoxylated carbonyl group.

In case of bond C, the effect of negatively charged 'O' atom (at 1) pushing > C = O group out of plane causing less resonance interaction with adjacent methoxyl group seems to be operative. The carbonyl band is thus observed at 1690 cm⁻¹ due to a shift of about

25 cm^{-1} from the benzeneoid *o*-methoxylated carbonyl band (1665 cm^{-1}). The resonance interaction effect is completely negated.

In case of bond A the bulky methyl group at 4 position pushes the methoxy group at 5 position out of the plane thus causing less resonance interaction with adjacent carbonyl group at the 6-position. This seems to explain a shift of band to a higher frequency by 15 cm^{-1} . Thus the $\Delta\nu_{\nu=0}$ value (15+35) for bond A is accounted for.

In case of 5-methoxy-6-acetylcoumarin, where there is no possibility of steric interference affecting the normal resonance interaction between $\text{O}-\text{OCH}_3$ and $> \text{C} = \text{O}$, the band observed is at 1667 cm^{-1} . Shift for band A being of the order of that of a normal benzeneoid bond. Also, bond B has no possibility for such steric interaction. Hence it has $\Delta\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}} = 0$ value of the same order (35 cm^{-1}) as that for normal benzene bond.

The absorption frequencies for *o*-methoxy-carbonyl and *o*-hydroxy-carbonyl on bond B also correspond to those for *o*-methoxy-acetophenone and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone respectively.

Bond D has a very high double bond character. The magnitude of band shift due to chelation may be explained on this account alone. Both the $> \text{C} = \text{O}$ band at 1686 cm^{-1} , and $\text{C} = \text{C}$ - band at 1603 cm^{-1} of 3-acetyl-coumarin are missing in 4-hydroxy-3-acetylcoumarin. Instead a new band at 1615 cm^{-1} appears which seems to have resulted due to overlapping of carbonyl and $\text{C} = \text{C}$ bands. The strong hydrogen bonding also explains the fact that the hydroxy group could not be methylated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting points are uncorrected. The compounds were crystallised until sharp and constant melting point and a single spot on TLC were obtained.

8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-3,4-dihydrocoumarin: Finely powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (3 g; 0.0225 mole) was added slowly to a solution of 2,6-dihydroxyacetophenone (1.5 g; 0.01 mole), acrylonitrile (2 g; 0.04 mole) and ether (40 ml.) which was continued to be stirred at 10–15°. Dry hydrogen chloride was bubbled through, when a clear solution resulted. Ether was slowly removed first at 60–65° and later at 100° in an oil-bath when a viscous slurry resulted. The temperature was gradually raised to 145–50°; heating was continued maintaining the current of hydrogen chloride through the whole reaction period. After 4–5 hours the whole mass became a glassy solid, which was kept as such at room temperature overnight. The mixture was decomposed by boiling with 30 ml. 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid, extracted with ether and the ethereal layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue, after the removal of solvent, on vacuum sublimation (200°/0.5 mm) gave a solid which on crystallisation from benzene—pet. ether (1 : 1), yielded 1 g. of *8-acetyl-7-hydroxy-3,4-dihydrocoumarin*, m.p. 127–28°. (Found : C, 64.26; H, 5.09. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 64.07; H, 4.89). The IR spectrum showed bands at 1775 cm^{-1} (lactone) and 1620 cm^{-1} (hydrogen bonded ketone).

8-Acetyl-7-hydroxycoumarin: A mixture of 8-acetyl-7-hydroxy-3,4-dihydrocoumarin (1 g), 10% Pd/C (0.6 g.) and diphenyl oxide (20 ml.) was heated under reflux for 6 hr. The catalyst was removed from the hot solution. Removal of diphenyl oxide under reduced

pressure yielded 0.8 g. (80%) solid which on crystallisation from ethanol melted at 165°. Mixed m.p. with authentic 7-hydroxy-8-acetyloumarin was undepressed.

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